

HORIZON 2020

Research and Innovation action

Grant Agreement No. 730965

ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium:

**A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research
in the Arctic**

**Deliverable 4.4. ARICE call for ship-time proposals
opened**

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	WP4
Deliverable no. & title	D4.4. ARICE Call for ship-time proposals opened
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Lead Beneficiary	AWI (partner 1)
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Deliverable No. 4.4.

ARICE call for ship time proposals opened

Abstract

The ARICE call for ship time proposals opened on the 12th of April 2018. The call was widely distributed by email to project partners, representatives of international polar programmes and projects, the European Polar Board and researchers for information and further distribution.

[View this email in your browser](#)

**ARICE Call for
Ship-Time
Proposals 2018
NOW OPEN!!**

**Fully Funded Transnational Access to the
Research Icebreakers CCGS Amundsen,
RV Sikuliaq and PRV Polarstern**

The EU Project **ARICE** opens now a call for ship-time proposals to access the icebreakers **CCGS Amundsen, RV Sikuliaq and PRV Polarstern**. This call will remain open until the 5th of July 2018.

Applications are welcome from **international teams of researchers and industry partners** from all career stages. Female applicants are encouraged to apply.

Check full eligibility criteria and funding conditions at: <https://www.arice.eu/apply-for-ship-time>

The access to PRV Polarstern is offered in the frame of the Multidisciplinary drifting Observatory for the Study of Arctic Climate (MOSAiC) Expedition, the first year-round expedition into the central Arctic exploring the Arctic climate system. Specific access regulations to PRV Polarstern in the frame of MOSAiC apply. Further information at <https://www.arice.eu/apply-for-ship-time>

NOTE: Proposals submitted to ARICE for PRV Polarstern will require a Confirmation of Endorsement from MOSAiC, a process which is encouraged to be started by potential applicants as soon as possible, as the endorsement process is expected to take 3 weeks from the submission of the request for endorsement until endorsement is confirmed. Detailed information is available at <https://www.arice.eu/apply-for-ship-time>

Contact: info@arice.eu

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